

PERCEIVED PHYSICAL LITERACY OF NOTRE DAME OF MARBEL UNIVERSITY COLLEGE STUDENTS

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Perceived Physical Literacy of Notre Dame of Marbel University College Students

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Abstract

This study described the level of perceived physical literacy of NDMU students. A descriptive research design was employed to determine this level. The researcher purposefully selected the respondents from the Socio-Cultural and Sports Club Varsity at Notre Dame of Marbel University using the adapted survey questionnaire. The perceived physical literacy among NDMU students is very high, which means that the students have knowledge and understanding, self-expression and communication with others, and a sense of self and self-confidence. This means that the students understand the benefits of physical activity, establish friendships with others, and are willing to play sports for health reasons.

Keywords: *perceived physical literacy, self-expression, communication, physical activity*

Introduction

Physical literacy, comprising motivation, confidence, physical competence, knowledge, and understanding, is the foundation for a lifelong engagement in physical activities. However, the benefits of physical activity need to be more widely understood (Roetert et al., 2018). The role of physical literacy in an individual's development and quality of life is of paramount importance. However, there is still a need for exploration to determine its role in promoting physical activity and enhancing health and well-being (Cornish et al., 2020).

In Turkey, students' physical literacy increases when they are more regularly engaged in sports (Cengiz, 2023). In addition, the perceived physical literacy among Hong Kong adolescents is low but significantly related to physical levels (Choi et al., 2018). According to Li et al. (2021), engaging in physical activity can sustain the development of physical literacy of Chinese students. Moreover, when physical literacy is high, there are higher levels of physical activity among children and adults aged 8-12 years (Longmuir et al., 2015).

In the Philippines, physical literacy is more prevalent with physical fitness, body management, folk dancing, and sports (Atienza, 2019). In addition, the physical literacy program is effective in enhancing power, balance, and speed (Alpe & Alforja, 2021).

Moreover, knowledge and understanding of physical literacy are significant for successful participation in and value of physical activities (Cale & Harris, 2018). In addition, according to Gilic et al. (2022), higher physical literacy among adolescents leads to better physical fitness and emphasizes the importance of developing cognitive and affective domains in physical education.

This study described the perceived physical literacy of the students at Notre Dame of Marbel University regarding physical literacy. Its significance is that understanding physical literacy among NDMU students will improve their quality of life.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive research design. Watson (2015) states that quantitative research encompasses a range of methods for systematically investigating social phenomena using numerical or statistical data. It describes and analyzes numerical data to answer the questions. The adapted questionnaire was used to measure the perceived physical literacy among NDMU students. To assess the perceived physical literacy, an instrument was derived from Sum et al. (2016) titled Perceived Physical Literacy. The construct reliability was acceptable, with Cronbach alpha of 0.82. The tool was a 15-item set distributed into three (3) sections.

Respondents

The respondents were purposefully selected from the Socio-Cultural and Sports Club Varsity at Notre Dame of Marbel University. Based on the solving using Slovin's formula, there are 201 members in the socio-cultural and sports varsity as respondents to the survey. However, only 130 members of the various groups responded to the survey.

Further, to attain homogeneity, the following quantitative criteria were considered: the researchers will have criteria to have a basis for their respondents, which is that he or she must be a member of socio-cultural and sports club varieties in NDMU who are on the recent list for the varsity year 2023-2024. He or she must be active in the club or varsity. Moreover, the quantitative criteria are as follows: he or she must be a member of the socio-cultural and sports programs at NDMU and a varsity from 2023-2024. He or she must be active in training and the program.

Data Analysis

In this study, descriptive statistics were used to describe the perceived physical literacy of NDMU students. Specifically, the mean was Cause et al.

used to determine the students' perceived physical literacy. In addition, the standard deviation (SD) measured the spread of the data distribution and was used to determine how varied the participants' responses were.

Results and Discussion

The level of Perceived Physical Literacy of NDMU students

The level of knowledge and understanding of perceived physical literacy of NDMU students, as reflected in Table 1, has a mean of 4.75, which is described as very high, which means that the level of knowledge and understanding is always observed. In addition, self-expression and communication with others have a mean of 4.44, which is described as very high, which means that self-expression and communication with others are always observed. Moreover, the sense of self and self-confidence has a mean of 4.27, which is described as very high; the result means that the sense of self and self-confidence is always observed. Finally, the overall mean of perceived physical literacy of NDMU students is 4.49, which is described as very high. The result means that the perceived physical literacy is always observed.

Table 1. *The level of Perceived Physical Literacy of NDMU students*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Descriptive Level</i>
Knowledge and Understanding	4.75	0.42	Very High
Self-Expression and Communication with Others	4.44	0.72	Very High
Sense of Self and Self Confidence	4.27	0.76	Very High
Overall	4.49	0.63	Very High

The study found that NDMU students have very high perceived physical literacy. This means that the students understand the benefits of physical activity, establish friendships with others, and are willing to play sports for health reasons. The result affirms the study of Öztürk (2023); when physical literacy is high, the more active a person performs physical activity. In addition, physical literacy with knowledge and understanding can positively impact the overall health and well-being of an individual (Roetert et al., 2018). Moreover, according to Pushkarenko et al. (2023), the students valued physical literacy for holistic well-being. Lastly, Physical Literacy is significant to the quality of life (Carreiro-Da-Costa, 2019).

Conclusions

The perceived physical literacy among NDMU students is high which means that the students have knowledge and understanding, self-expression and communication with others, and a sense of self and self-confidence. This study has potential implications for physical education teachers. The activities should be intensified to maintain the high result of perceived physical literacy among NDMU students.

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